

Research Methodology in Computing

Data Analysis

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Part 1 – Quantitative Analysis

1. Data Distribution

To analyse the data, provided in Table 1. As the data has been obtained from an experiment that compared two programming languages A and B while considering the variables i.e., program size, development time and the total number of defects. For the Data Distribution following steps are performed:

- All the data entered from the Table 1 into an MS Excel Sheet.

Table 1: Data for programming languages A and B				
Prog. Language	Program size(LOC)	Development time (minutes)	Total number of defects	
A	1408	3949	89	
A	1529	2061	69	
A	946	3869	170	
A	1141	5562	271	
A	696	5028	103	
A	775	2296	75	
A	1205	2980	79	
A	1159	2991	194	
A	862	2701	67	
A	1206	2592	77	
B	1316	3986	68	
B	1787	4477	54	
B	1105	3789	130	
B	1583	4371	48	
B	1381	3325	133	
B	944	5234	80	
B	1492	4901	64	
B	1217	3897	89	
B	936	3825	57	
B	1441	4015	79	

- While considering the variable program size following chart is generated.

Table 1: Data for programming languages A and B				
Prog. Language	Program size(LOC)	Development time (minutes)	Total number of defects	
A	1408	3949	89	
A	1529	2061	69	
A	946	3869	170	
A	1141	5562	271	
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A	775	2296	75	
A	1205	2980	79	
A	1159	2991	194	
A	862	2701	67	
A	1206	2592	77	
B	1316	3986	68	
B	1787	4477	54	
B	1105	3789	130	
B	1583	4371	48	
B	1381	3325	133	
B	944	5234	80	
B	1492	4901	64	
B	1217	3897	89	
B	936	3825	57	
B	1441	4015	79	

Discussion of results while comparing the programming languages LOC:

By analysis of charts it can be observed that the programming language A is more easy to implement the programs because it is using less lines of code as compared to language B so eventually that will result in short execution time.

- While considering the variable Development time(minutes) following chart is generated.

Prog. Language	Program size(LOC)	Development time (minutes)	Total number of defects
A	1408	3949	89
A	1529	2061	69
A	946	3869	170
A	1141	5562	271
A	696	5028	103
A	775	2296	75
A	1205	2980	79
A	1159	2991	194
A	862	2701	67
A	1206	2592	77
B	1316	3986	68
B	1787	4477	54
B	1105	3789	130
B	1583	4371	48
B	1381	3325	133
B	944	5234	80
B	1492	4901	64
B	1217	3897	89
B	936	3875	57
B	1441	4015	79

Discussion of results while comparing the programming languages Development time:

By analysis of charts it can be observed that the programming language A is more efficient and fast to because it is taking less time to develop the programs as compared to language B so eventually that will provide faster solutions and rapid market gain.

- While considering the variable and the total number of defects following chart is generated.

Discussion of results while comparing the programming languages:

By analysis of charts it can be observed that the programming language B is giving less defects or errors because it is giving less defects to develop the programs as compared to language A so eventually that will be more reliable programming language.

Overall Results

It can be concluded under the analysis and discussion that the programming language B is less error prone so although it is take more time to develop and more lines of code but saving time at the stage of testing and debugging of programs.

2. Statistical tests

Parametric test is selected because the data is normally distributed for the language A and Language B for all three variables program size, number of errors detected and development time as shown below. Statistical tests have been performed for all the variables through using parametric.

	Program size(LOC) Language A	Program size(LOC) Language B
	1408	1316
	1529	1787
	946	1105
	1141	1583
	696	1381
	775	944
	1205	1492
	1159	1217
	862	936
	1206	1441

Development time (minutes) for language A	Development time (minutes) for language B
3949	3986
2061	4477
3869	3789
5562	4371
5028	3325
2296	5234
2980	4901
2991	3897
2701	3825
2592	4015

Total number of defects	Total number of defects		
89	68		
69	54		
170	130		
271	48		
103	133		
75	80		
79	64		
194	89		
67	57		
77	79		

Statistical analysis using t-test:

LOC

Program size(LOC) Language A	Program size(LOC) Language B
1408	1316
1529	1787
946	1105
1141	1583
696	1381
775	944
1205	1492
1159	1217
862	936
1206	1441

Data Analysis

Analysis Tools

- Histogram
- Moving Average
- Random Number Generation
- Rank and Percentile
- Regression
- Sampling
- t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means
- t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances
- t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances**
- z-Test: Two Sample for Means

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
	Variable 1	Variable 2
Mean	1092.7	1320.2
Variance	72777.34	75653.95556
Observations	10	10
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	18	
t Stat	-1.86732	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.039115	
t Critical one-tail	1.734064	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.07823	
t Critical two-tail	2.100922	

Development time

Development time (minutes) for language A	Development time (minutes) for language B
3949	3986
2061	4477
3869	3789
5562	4371
5028	3325
2296	5234
2980	4901
2991	3897
2701	3825
2592	4015

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances

	Variable 1	Variable 2
Mean	3402.9	4182
Variance	1371420.989	323365.3
Observations	10	10
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	13	
t Stat	1.892499307	

P(T<=t) one-tail	0.040451932
t Critical one-tail	1.770933396
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.080903865
t Critical two-tail	2.160368656

Number of defects:

Total number of defects	Total number of defects
89	68
69	54
170	130
271	48
103	133
75	80
79	64
194	89
67	57
77	79

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances

	Variable 1	Variable 2
Mean	119.4	80.2
Variance	4776.488889	891.0667
Observations	10	10
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	12	
t Stat	1.646600239	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.06277924	
t Critical one-tail	1.782287556	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.12555848	
t Critical two-tail	2.17881283	

3. Mean, Median, Mode, and Standard Deviation

For LOC:

	Program size(LOC) Language A	Program size(LOC) Language B
	1408	1316
	1529	1787
	946	1105
	1141	1583
	696	1381
	775	944
	1205	1492
	1159	1217
	862	936
	1206	1441
Mean	1092.7	1320.2
Median	1150	1348.5
Mode	#N/A	#N/A
Standard Deviation	255.9289159	260.937847

For number of defects

	Total number of defects	Total number of defects
	89	68
	69	54
	170	130
	271	48
	103	133
	75	80
	79	64
	194	89
	67	57
	77	79
Mean	119.4	80.2
Median	84	73.5
Mode	#N/A	#N/A
Standard Deviation	65.56553973	28.31889828

For Development Time

	Development time (minutes) for language A	Development time (minutes) for language B
	3949	3986
	2061	4477
	3869	3789
	5562	4371
	5028	3325
	2296	5234
	2980	4901
	2991	3897
	2701	3825
	2592	4015
Mean	3402.9	4182
Median	2985.5	4000.5
Mode	#N/A	#N/A
Standard Deviation	1110.981048	539.4708519

4. Box plot and Whisker

A **Box and Whisker plot** is a way to visualize the spread of data, showing the median, quartiles, and any outliers, making it suitable for comparing the distributions of these variables between two programming languages.

Part 2 - Qualitative Analysis

1. Process Description

Thematic Analysis was used to analyze the challenges and best practices from the three provided papers.

Figure 1.1 : Thematic Analysis Steps

Thematic analysis was used to study the challenges and best practices mentioned in three papers related to industry-academia collaboration. First, the papers were carefully read to understand key points about the difficulties and positive strategies in such partnerships. Important phrases and sections were then highlighted and categorized with labels like "Management Engagement" and "Communication Barriers." These labels were grouped into broader themes, such as challenges in communication, the importance of management support, and the value of mutual learning. The themes were then refined to make sure they matched the findings from all three papers. Each theme was clearly defined with examples, such as how communication issues arise when academic and industry goals don't align and how management support is crucial for successful collaboration.

2. Thematic Map

Following Thematic Maps show the experience and lessons learned regarding Industry-Academia Collaboration found under the study of three research papers

References

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